

PACIFICUS

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- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
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“OVERACHIEVING WORLD: NICHE OF LITERARY WORKS”

A lot of us have been waiting for the world to take notice of our work. Standing between your writing process and the approval you have been desperately itching to chase. But what if we flipped that equation in us? Is this work worth it, even if no one is reading it? Will it be the breaking ground we have wanted to be fleeting?

Ever since I was little, I loved to scribble a bunch of words I did not imagine could turn out well. I remember it vividly. This summer, I was at the beach, looking at the sunset with a pen and a notebook in hand. The tall pines, further along the bay walk, were swaying in the fresh ocean breeze, creating a perfect view and vibe for writing. But under the circumstances of this era, I am not sure where all the butterflies in my stomach have gone whenever I opt to write a piece.

There exists an undeniable niche in contemporary literature of the twenty-first century. Strangely enough, it pulses with a chaotic, skeptical energy that reflects the instability of the current technological world. Reflecting the current state of today's digital advancements, everyone is overflowing with the crackle of enthusiasm built from their own unique points of view. And it is humorous why readers are intrigued by the very little detail of the blunt peroration, unbiased discourses all although it lacks realness and substance. Commonly, built like a bomb, explosive with authenticity or bluff, forcing narratives to create a different standpoint. Literary works have a different punch and pinch to every reader, in how they convey, connect, and communicate.

“What is in my mind?”, a statement that urges inquiry, validation, and truth. This is a big step towards literature. We are challenged through digital advancements, as it devours individuals' way of thinking, that an extreme effect on unveiling literary truth. Initially, it may have had a tolerable impact with globalization, but as time passed by, it unquestionably had a profound effect on globalization. Literary works revolve around a single idea of a writer/author, and through a personal and authentic piece, people will be inspired by having a glimpse of it, building a strong understanding and relationship from various cultures that uplifts diversity, which healthily caters to a vast tapestry of differences. We may have cultural differences, we may have been problematically experiencing language barriers, yet through literary pieces in this generation, we make it relatable and purposefully pave the way to constitute a reasonable narrative.

In fact, focusing on a single style and form of a literary piece will never be enough for a contemporary author in the digital age. We yearn for innovation, trends, and erratic excerpts, something that can punch you in the heart and mind. Willingly forge and own a genuine creative esplanade that follows the author's pages in the

pursuit of attaining an extensive knock-on reader's personal space. The minute they decide this is just like me, it is the true success of a contemporary work.

One of the prominent features of the twenty-first-century contemporary literature is the risqué and potential of technological advancements as it is. Through a social media platform, virtual surveillance, and digital mapping, anyone can be more than just an element; in fact, you will become the anchor. The process dissociates authors from the condition that all aspects must be true to “what is going on,” providing room for a more complex and poignant self-assessment.

We already know the truth, that at this point, with the existence of digitalization, some may retaliate since the author and readers are not on the same page. This technological era might seem a bit dry, desolate, and sand-scorched desert as it withheld a tremendous count of points of view, unsolicited advice, and rescinded validations that leave authors/writers gasping and parched for even a slight breath of air. It is dawning on us that on any day, at any time, our literary works can be owned or copied by someone else. But let me be clear in here, the desire to show your originality, your blueprint into life, will ground into your well-being as a writer. Now, if you run from your story long enough, sooner or later you will find yourself at a table where you thought you were further and that everything is falling into its place. And for a brief second of reprieve, you will feel the need to ask yourself, “Is it still what I wanted it to be?” Make sure to move away from comfort and step out of it, because not doing it shows you are quitting. This is for you, a writer/author who is tired of change but wants to be the overachieving writer in the world of niche literary works here, in the 21st century.

